

Research

Laparoscopic Versus Open Cholecystectomy for Acute Cholecystitis

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Abstract: Objective: To investigate the value of laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) for acute cholecystitis.

Methods: The clinical data of 67 patients undergoing LC and 58 patients undergoing open cholecystectomy (OC) from January 2021 to December 2023 in the Janaki Medical College and Teaching Hospital were retrospectively reviewed. The operation time, blood loss, intestinal peristalsis recovery time, hospital stay, analgesic administration and complications were compared between the two groups.

Results: In LC group, 64 cases went through the surgery successfully, and 3 cases were converted to laparotomy including 2 cases of severe adhesions of Calot Triangle and difficult separation and 1 case of hemostasis difficulty under laparoscope due to massive gallbladder bed bleeding. There were 1 case of postoperative incision infection (1.6%), and 1 case of biliary leakage (1.6%). The incidence of complication was 3.1% (2/64). In OC group, there were 4 cases of incision infection (6.9%), 1 case of abdominal residual abscess (1.7%), 2 cases of biliary leakage (3.4%) and 2 cases of adhesive intestinal obstruction (3.4%). The incidence of complication of OC group was 15.5% (9 / 58), significantly higher than that of LC group ($X^2=5.696, P=0.017$). Compared with OC group, LC group had shorter operative time [(42.6±12.3)min vs. (63.8±11.6)min, $t=-9.767, P=0.000$], less blood loss [(47.8±11.5)ml vs. (76.3±14.2)ml, $t=-12.231, P=0.000$], shorter intestinal peristalsis recovery time [(24.2±3.7)h vs. (43.7±8.6)h, $t=-16.535, P=0.000$], shorter postoperative hospital stay [(4.6±2.2)d vs. (9.1±3.4)d, $t=-8.758, P=0.000$] and lower administration ratio of postoperative analgesic [20.3% (13/64) vs. 48.3% (28/58), $X^2=10.663, P=0.001$].

Conclusion: Compared with OC, LC has minimal trauma, quicker recovery, shorter hospital stay, fewer complications for the treatment of acute cholecystitis.

Keywords: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy; open cholecystectomy; Acute cholecystitis

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Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is a treatment of choice for symptomatic cholelithiasis. LC is one of the most commonly done operations in our country. LC has been described as the most significant major surgical advance of the 1990s which allows shorter hospitalization; rapid recovery and early return to work along with financial saving[1]. At present, in our institute, almost all cases of symptomatic cholelithiasis are done laparoscopically with a conversion rate

of less than one percent. There are several papers describing the outcomes like pain, length of hospital stays, complications, etc. in various clinical settings and patient groups available[2–7]. Patient-reported quality of life is an important outcome measure following all medical and surgical interventions.⁸ However, there are only a few papers available addressing quality of life-issues following laparoscopic cholecystectomy[8–15].

Research Methodology

From January 2021 to December 2023 in the Janaki Medical College and Teaching Hospital performed laparoscopic cholecystectomy on 67 cases of acute cholecystitis and compared the results with those of 58 cases of open cholecystectomy (OC) during the same period. This study aimed to explore the clinical value of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in acute cholecystitis.

Inclusion criteria: ①Disease course ≤ 5 days; ②No symptoms of shock and systemic poisoning, no serious organic lesions of important organs such as heart, lung, brain; ③Normal coagulation function; ④No gallbladder perforation or gangrene; ⑤No history of upper abdominal surgery; ⑥No biliary stones by B-ultrasound or CT examination, and pancreatitis was excluded. According to the patient's wishes, they were divided into LC group (n=67) and OC group (n=58).

LC group: general anesthesia, four-hole method, pneumoperitoneum pressure 12-15 mm Hg (1 mm Hg=0.133 kPa). Explore the abdominal cavity, evaluate the inflammation and adhesion of the gallbladder, and check whether there are any combined diseases of other organs. Close to the gallbladder, bluntly separate the surrounding adhesions, and move gently to avoid accidental injury. For those with excessive tension of the gallbladder, puncture and decompress first to facilitate grasping. Use an aspirator to push and suck to bluntly separate the Calot triangle near the ampulla, distinguish the cystic duct and the cystic artery, and cut it off after clamping; for those with a thick and short cystic duct, do not blindly clamp and cut it. Clearly identify the relationship between the cystic duct and the common bile duct and common hepatic duct before clamping the cystic duct. Ligating the cystic duct with silk thread and then clamping the cystic duct with titanium clips or absorbable clips. The gallbladder was removed and electrocoagulated at the bleeding site of the gallbladder bed, and the abdominal cavity was flushed. After confirming that there was no bleeding and bile leakage, a silicone tube was placed in the Winslow hole and led out from the hole on the right anterior axillary line. OC group: general anesthesia, conventional open cholecystectomy, and silicone tube drainage was placed after surgery. Observation indicators ① Operation time: the time from skin incision to suturing the incision; ② Intraoperative bleeding: the sum of the amount of blood sucked by the suction device during the operation and the amount of blood seepage using gauze (each piece of gauze was completely soaked during the operation, and the estimated blood loss was about 15 ml); ③ Postoperative analgesic use: the patient could not tolerate pain and required the use of any analgesic, with no limit on the number of times used; ④ Intestinal peristalsis recovery time: that is, the time of the first anal gas discharge after surgery; ⑤ Postoperative hospitalization time: abdominal pain disappeared, body temperature was normal, incision was dry, there was no infection or rupture, and the patient could be discharged after the blood routine examination was normal; ⑥ Complications. SPSS 29.0 software was used for statistical methods. Measurement data were expressed by Goss s and two independent sample t tests, and count data were expressed by p2 test. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

All 125 cases in the two groups had right upper abdominal pain, right upper abdominal tenderness, and Mushy sign (+) on physical examination. In the LC group, 47 cases had a body temperature of 37.5-39.4°C (70.1%), 56 cases had white blood cells $(10.6-21.8) \times 10^9/L$ (83.6%), 12 cases had hypertension (17.9%), 3 cases had coronary artery atherosclerosis (CHD) (4.5%), and 5 cases had diabetes (7.5%). In the OC group, 41 cases had a body temperature of 37.5-39.6°C (70.7%), 48 cases had white blood cells $(10.2-22.4) \times 10^9/L$ (82.8%), 10 cases had hypertension (17.2%), 2 cases

had CHD (3.4%), and 3 cases had diabetes (5.2%). Ultrasound or CT examinations of 125 cases showed gallbladder enlargement and thick wall. 97 cases (77.6%) had gallbladder stones, but none had bile duct stones. 6 cases (4.8%) had bile duct dilatation, and MRCP examinations ruled out bile duct stones. Postoperative pathological examinations confirmed acute cholecystitis. There was no significant difference in general data such as gender, age, course of disease, body temperature, white blood cell count, and complications between the two groups ($P>0.05$), were comparable, see Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of general data between the two groups ($\bar{x}\pm s$)

Groups	Age(years)	Male	Female	Duration(d)	Temperature >37.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	WBC $>$ $10.0\times 10^9/\text{L}$	Complication
LC (n=67)	46.3 $\pm$ 11.6	29	38	1.3 $\pm$ 0.8	47	56	20
OC (n=58)	45.7 $\pm$ 12.4	26	32	1.4 $\pm$ 0.6	41	48	15
t(χ^2) value	t = 0.279	$\chi^2 = 0.030$		t = -0.781	$\chi^2 = 0.004$	$\chi^2 = 0.015$	$\chi^2 = 0.245$
P value	0.781	0.862		0.437	0.947	0.902	0.620

In the LC group, 64 cases were successfully treated, and 3 cases (4.5%) were converted to laparotomy (2 cases had dense adhesions in Calot's triangle that were difficult to separate due to unclear anatomical relationships, and 1 case had a lot of bleeding in the gallbladder bed that was difficult to stop bleeding under the microscope). During the operation, cholecystitis and ovarian cysts were found in 2 cases, and ovarian cysts were removed at the same time. In the LC group, 1 case (1.6%, 1/64) of postoperative incision infection was cured after active dressing change; 1 case (1.6%, 1/64) of bile leakage was drained on the first day after surgery. 60 ml of bile-like fluid was drained, which gradually decreased afterwards. After 6 days of continuous drainage, the tube was removed and the patient was cured. In the OC group, 4 cases (6.9%, 4/58) had postoperative wound infection, which was cured by enhanced dressing change and secondary suture of the wound; 1 case (1.7%, 1/58) had residual abdominal abscess, which was absorbed after B-ultrasound positioning drainage and enhanced anti-infection; 2 cases (3.4%, 2/58) had bile leakage, with a drainage volume of 50-80 ml/d. After 6-8 days of indwelling drainage tube, the tube was removed and the patient recovered; 2 cases (3.4%, 2/58) had paroxysmal abdominal pain, anal cessation of gas and defecation, and were diagnosed with adhesive intestinal obstruction by physical examination, abdominal radiography and other imaging examinations, and were cured after conservative treatment. The LC group was superior to the OC group in terms of operation time, intraoperative bleeding, postoperative analgesic use rate, intestinal peristalsis recovery time, postoperative hospitalization time and complications, as shown in Table 2. 125 cases were followed up for 3 to 20 months after surgery, with an average of 6 months. No abdominal pain, jaundice or other discomfort was found, and no abnormalities were found in blood routine examinations and ultrasound.

Table 2 Comparison of surgical conditions between the two groups ($\bar{x}\pm s$)

Groups	Operation time(min)	Blood Loss(ml)	Postoperative Analgesics(%)	Recovery Time(hrs)	Hospital Stay (d)	Complication (%)
LC (n=64)	42.6 $\pm$ 12.3	47.8 $\pm$ 11.5	13(20.3)	24.2 $\pm$ 3.7	4.6 $\pm$ 2.2	2(3.1)
OC (n=61)	63.8 $\pm$ 11.6	76.3 $\pm$ 14.2	28(48.3)	43.7 $\pm$ 8.6	9.1 $\pm$ 3.4	9(15.5)
t(χ^2) value	t = -9.767	t=12.231	$\chi^2 = 10.663$	t = -16.535	t= -8.758	$\chi^2 = 5.696$
P value	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.017

Discussion

There is controversy about LC in the treatment of acute cholecystitis[4]. In the past, it was believed that during acute cholecystitis, the gallbladder wall was obviously congested and edematous, with high tension, unclear local anatomical relationships, and a lot of bleeding during the operation, which increased the difficulty of the operation. Therefore, it was once considered a contraindication for LC. In recent years, with the development of LC technology, the

improvement of surgical skills and the accumulation of surgical experience, LC is feasible for acute cholecystitis, and the treatment effect is better than traditional open cholecystectomy[6]. This study compared the two surgical procedures of LC and OC and believed that LC has the following advantages: ① The laparoscopic field of view is wide, the exploration is comprehensive, and it is not affected by the position of the gallbladder and obesity. There is no need to expand the incision, which is conducive to the complete removal of the lesion; at the same time, other organ diseases can be explored and combined surgery can be performed. In this study, 2 cases of cholecystitis combined with ovarian cysts were treated in the LC group, and the combined surgery was effective. ② Few complications. Sun Kai et al reported that the incidence of postoperative complications in the LC group was 8.00%, which was significantly lower than that in the OC group (22.00%) ($P<0.05$). Hu Shengliang et al reported that the incidence of postoperative complications in the LC group and the OC group was 6.25% and 22.92%, respectively, with a statistical difference ($P=0.014$). In this study, the incidence of complications in the LC group was 3.1%, and that in the OC group was 15.5%, with a significant difference ($P<0.05$). Incision infection and bile leakage are common complications after acute cholecystitis surgery, especially incision infection. In this study, there was only one case of postoperative incision infection in the LC group (1.6%, 1/64), while there were four cases of postoperative incision infection in the OC group (6.9%, 4/58). Analysis may be related to the small puncture hole in the LC, the seamless incision, and the isolation of the trocar, which avoids the contamination of the incision by pus and bile. ③ The operation has little trauma, less intraoperative bleeding, mild postoperative pain, and patients can get out of bed and move early; the operation has little interference with organs, the operation time is short, which is conducive to the recovery of intestinal function and the patient recovers quickly after operation. In this study, the operation time, intraoperative bleeding, postoperative intestinal peristalsis recovery time, postoperative analgesic use and hospitalization time of the LC group were better than those of the OC group ($P<0.05$).

Experience of LC surgery: ① During acute attack of cholecystitis, there is obvious edema and poor brittleness. There is a lot of exudation and bleeding during surgery. It is necessary to emphasize maintaining a clear surgical field, clearly exposing the bleeding site or showing the anatomical relationship, and avoid blindly clamping the tissue to avoid accidental injury. ② When separating adhesions around the gallbladder, keep close to the gallbladder and use a combination of blunt and sharp methods to separate. Ju Jianming reported that the use of electrocoagulation hook, suction device and ultrasonic knife to separate adhesions has a significant effect. Approach and dissect from the gallbladder ampulla to the proximal end of the cystic duct, use the suction device to push and scrape the gallbladder triangle bluntly, expose the cystic duct and cystic artery, and distinguish the relationship between the "three tubes" before handling the cystic duct. The operation should be careful and gentle, and avoid excessive force to avoid injuring the cystic artery and bile duct. ③ Drainage tubes were placed in all LC groups, and 1 case had bile leakage. After adequate drainage, the tube was removed and healed after 6 days. Acute cholecystitis causes inflammatory edema, excessive exudation and bleeding on the wound surface, or intraoperative decompression causes bile or gravel to leak out and contaminate the abdominal cavity, and sometimes even bile leakage from the capillary bile duct. Therefore, routine placement of drainage tubes can timely drain inflammatory exudate and reduce the occurrence of infection or residual abscesses. At the same time, it can also observe whether there is bleeding or bile leakage after surgery, so as to deal with it in a timely and effective manner. Li Xinmin et al. reported that the conversion rate of LC to laparotomy was 6.4%, and the conversion rate of LC to laparotomy in this study was 4.5%. Conversion to laparotomy is to ensure safety and does not mean surgical failure. For cases such as difficult separation of dense adhesions in Calot's triangle, severe adhesions around the gallbladder, suspected bile duct injury, and difficult-to-control bleeding during surgery, conversion to laparotomy should be performed without hesitation, and the pursuit of laparoscopy to complete the surgery should be avoided, which may cause irreversible secondary injuries. In summary, compared with OC, LC has the advantages of less trauma, faster recovery, and fewer complications, and is worthy of outcomes in hospitals.

Conclusion

Compared with OC, LC has minimal trauma, quicker recovery, shorter hospital stay, fewer complications for the treatment of acute cholecystitis.

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